

THE APPLICATIVE VALUE OF CLINICAL AND PROGNOSTIC STRATIFICATION SCORES IN PATIENTS WITH EXTRANODAL AGGRESSIVE NON-HODGKIN'S LYMPHOMA

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Abstract

Introduction.

Non-Hodgkin lymphomas (NHL) are a heterogeneous group of lymphoproliferative disorders originating from B, T or natural killer (NK) lymphocytes. Clinical scoring systems have been developed to better stratify the patients' risk and help select therapeutic strategies.

Materials and methods.

Clinical and prognostic stratification scores were applied to 99 patients with extranodal aggressive NHL. The diagnosis was confirmed morphologically by tumor biopsy and immunohistochemistry.

Results.

IPI is an independent prognostic factor for progression-free survival. In addition, it facilitates the investigation of the independent impact of other prognostic biomarkers through adjusted analyses. Calculating International Prognostic Index (IPI), we obtained the following results: IPI 0 – 25% and IPI1 – 23.2% with a low risk and 5-year survival of 73%, IPI2 – 18.1% with low intermediate risk and 5-year survival of 51% , IPI3 – 17.1% with high intermediate risk and 5-year survival of 43%, IPI4 – 12.1% and IPI 5 – 4.5% with high risk and 5-year survival of 26%.

Conclusions.

Clinical scoring systems allow better risk stratification of patients and selection of appropriate therapeutic strategies. The IPI is a clinical tool developed to help predict the prognosis of patients with aggressive NHL. R-IPI is a clinically useful prognostic index that allows guiding treatment planning in patients with DLBCL.

Keywords: Aggressive non-Hodgkin's lymphoma, extranodal, clinical stratification scores, IPI, R-IPI, ECOG

What is not yet known on the issue addressed in the submitted manuscript: Demonstrating the importance of applying clinical and prognostic stratification scores in patients with aggressive extranodal NHL for treatment planning and survival estimation.

The research hypothesis – A study was performed on a group of 99 patients with a morphologically and immunohistochemically confirmed diagnosis of extranodal aggressive NHL applying clinical and prognostic stratification scores.

The novelty added by manuscript to the already published scientific literature

Performing a complex analysis on the research group with the application of clinical stratification scores and reporting the data obtained to those from the specialized literature demonstrating the need to use them in medical practice.

Introduction

Non-Hodgkin's lymphomas (NHL) are a heterogeneous group of lymphoproliferative disorders originating from B, T or natural killer (NK) lymphocytes[1]. NHL are one of the most common forms of hemoblastosis. Studies have shown that every year 15 cases of the disease are detected per 100,000 inhabitants. The risk of developing NHL increases with age. The average age of onset of the disease is between 60 and 65 years. The disease is much more common in men than in women[2].

Clinical scoring systems have been developed to better stratify the patients' risk and help select therapeutic strategies[3].

The International Prognostic Index (IPI) scoring system was first published 25 years ago and remains widely used today. The IPI score assigns 1 point to each adverse prognostic factor (age > 60 years), serum lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) above the upper limit, stage III/IV according to Ann Arbor classification, Eastern Cooperative Oncology Group (ECOG) performance scale ≥ 2 and > 1 (with extranodal involvement) and classifies patients into 4 risk groups based on the total score: 0/1 = low risk, 2 = low intermediate risk, 3 = high intermediate risk and 4/5 = high risk[4].

The addition of rituximab to cyclophosphamide, doxorubicin, vincristine, and prednisone (R-CHOP) changed the clinical history of DLBCL, significantly extending survival and increasing the patient's cure rate [5]. The revised IPI (R-IPI) was developed specifically for patients newly diagnosed with DLBCL to better stratify risk in those who have been treated with R-CHOP. The R-IPI used the same risk factors and scoring system as the IPI, but redistributed the scores to form 3 risk groups: 0 = very good risk, 1/2 = good risk, and 3/4/5 = poor risk . R-IPI was reported to be less complex than IPI and performed better than IPI in distinguishing patients with more or less favorable long-

term outcomes[6]. Researchers around the world consider the ECOG Performance Scale when planning cancer clinical trials to study new treatment regimens. This numbering scale is a way to define the population of patients included in the study and to guide physicians enrolling patients in these studies[7]. It is also a way for doctors to track changes in the patient's level of functioning as a result of treatment during the study[8]. This is how the results are interpreted: 0—Fully active, able to carry out all pre-disease performance without restrictions; 1—restricted in strenuous physical activities, but ambulatory and able to carry out activities of a light or sedentary nature, for example, light housework, office work; 2 — able to take care of himself, but unable to carry out work activities; more than 50% of waking hours; 3—limited personal care capacity; confined to bed or chair for more than 50% of waking hours; 4—completely disabled; cannot take care of himself; totally confined to bed or chair; 5—dead[9].

Purpose : it consists in applying the clinical and prognostic stratification scores to patients with extranodal aggressive NHL for a more correct evaluation and in order to select an appropriate therapy.

Materials and Methods : Clinical and prognostic stratification scores were applied to 99 patients with extranodal aggressive NHL. The diagnosis was confirmed morphologically by tumor biopsy and immunohistochemistry. The degree of spread of the tumor process was determined according to the International Clinical Classification adopted in the city of Ann Arbor (USA), in 1971. Clinical, radiological and ultrasound examinations, spinal tap, trepanobiopsy of the iliac bone, endoscopic or radiological research of the gastrointestinal tract, fibroepipharyngoscopy were used to stage the tumor process, determine the areas of initial metastasis and also, in the stage of generalization of NHL.

Results and discussion

We are witnessing a continuous increase in the incidence of hemoblastoses, with NHL occupying the first place. Annually, the number of patients primarily diagnosed with aggressive NHL is on the rise, and at the same time, the number of treatment-resistant cases also increases, which requires a more detailed research of them as well as the discovery of new treatment schemes. In the research group, 99 patients were selected according to the following criteria: patients with the diagnosis of extranodal aggressive NHL confirmed morphologically and immunohistochemically, the patient's age over 18 years, his informed consent. The average age of the group of patients was 60 years, with a slight predominance of the female sex (male-female ratio 1:1.27). At the same time, the most frequent type of aggressive lymphoma in our clinic turned out to be lymphoblastic in 55.5%, followed by diffuse large B-cell lymphoma (DLBCL) - 33.3%, T-cell lymphoma was diagnosed in 7.07%, and the other types of lymphoma (NOS lymphoma, grade IIIB follicular, from the mantle zone, plasmablastic) each of them constituting less than 1% [fig. 1].

It was found that of the extranodal lesions, the most frequent is the involvement of the gastro-intestinal tract (GIT) - 37.35%, of its anatomical segments, the stomach is most often affected (32.3%). The 2nd place among the extranodal locations is occupied by the

Waldeyer lymphatic ring - 24.24%, of the formations of the ring, the involvement of the nasopharynx was most often observed - 13.13%, followed by the damage to the palatine tonsils - 10.1%. Soft tissues as primary damage by NHL were observed in 7.07%, followed by skin and bone tissue each returning 6.06%, CNS- 4.4%, and the other locations (lacrimal gland, mammary gland, liver, kidneys, testicle, parotid gland, etc.) constitute on average less than 1% each [fig. 2].

In the study, the presence of B symptoms was noted in 26.27% of patients, while their absence was observed in 73.73% (A- no symptoms of general intoxication)[fig. 3]. Although patients diagnosed with aggressive extranodal NHL tend to present themselves to the doctor at a lower stage than those with primary damage to the lymph nodes, the statistics are quite worrying, because 35% of patients presented at stage I, followed by those in stage IV which constituted - 31%, in stage II - 29.3% and stage III - 4.7% [fig. 4].

We also found that extranodal aggressive NHLs tend to metastasize more frequently in lymph nodes - 42.8%, followed by soft tissues - 20%, Waldeyer's lymphatic ring - 11.42%, liver - 8.57%, CNS - 5.71%, lung tissue - 5.71%, spleen - 2.8%.

For a more accurate stratification of the risk of patients with aggressive extranodal NHL, for the evaluation of the prognosis, the survival rate, but also for the correct choice of treatment schemes, we applied the clinical scoring systems.

IPI has stood the test of time. It is used in most studies to stratify risk and ensure balance between groups. IPI is an independent prognostic factor for progression-free survival. In addition, it facilitates the investigation of the independent impact of other prognostic biomarkers through adjusted analyzes [10]. Thus, for the estimation of the IPI score, we applied the following factors: age (one point was given to people over 60), 41 patients over 60 were enrolled in the research group, which constituted 41.4%. The level of LDH was also evaluated, and its increase above the reference value was observed in 33.4% of cases. As previously mentioned, 35.7% of patients were diagnosed in stages III/IV according to the Ann Arbor classification. An important role for the assessment of the IPI score is the ECOG performance scale, according to which the patient's assessment is carried out on a range from 0 to 5. After interpreting the results we obtained: ECOG 0 - 17.1% of patients were fully active, able to carry out all pre-illness performances without restrictions. ECOG 1- we noted in 52.5% people, which implies that they have restrictions in strenuous physical activities, but ambulatory they are able to carry out activities of a light or sedentary nature. ECOG 2- in 24.2% cases, these patients are able to take care of themselves, but unable to carry out work activities. ECOG 3 - 6.2%, they have limited personal care capacity; confined to bed or chair. ECOG 4 and 5 were not assigned to any person. Thus, applying the data listed above, we calculated the International Prognostic Index (IPI) obtaining the following results: IPI 0 - 25% and respectively IPI1 - 23.2% having a low risk and survival at 5 years of 73%, IPI2 - 18.1% with low intermediate risk and 5-year survival of 51%, IPI3 - 17.1% with high intermediate risk and

5-year survival of 43%, IPI4 – 12.1% and respectively IPI 5 – 4.5% high risk and 5-year survival of 26%.

The Revised International Prognostic Index (R-IPI) was developed to predict the outcome of people receiving rituximab with chemotherapy. The score is able to differentiate patients into three groups (very good, good, poor), all of which have >50% survival in the new era of rituximab[11]. In the study group, 16 patients with the diagnosis of DLBCL were enrolled, who were treated according to the R-CHOP scheme, in their case the R-IPI prognostic index was applied. According to the calculations, 18.75% of patients have a very good prognosis (progression-free survival (PFS) at 4 years of 94%, overall survival (OS) 94%), 56.25% a good prognosis (PFS at 4 years 80%, OS 79%) and 25% a poor prognosis (4-year PFS 53%, OS 55%). In the era of R-CHOP treatment, R-IPI is a clinically useful prognostic index that can help guide treatment planning and interpretation of clinical trials[12].

Conclusions

1. Clinical scoring systems allow better risk stratification of patients and selection of appropriate therapeutic strategies.

2. The IPI is a clinical tool developed to help predict the prognosis of patients with aggressive NHL.

3. R-IPI is a clinically useful prognostic index that allows guiding treatment planning in patients with DLBCL.

4. Patients diagnosed in early stages (I/II) have a higher progression-free survival rate compared to those diagnosed in stages III/IV.

Authors' contribution

Urescu Dumitrita studied the bibliographic reference sources, summarized and systematized the data of published researches, studies and clinical recommendations, collected the data, structured and drafted the article.

Vasile Musteata, Maria Robu, Larisa Musteata, Natalia Sporis, Irina Cebanu conceptualized the manuscript, summarized and systematized the data of published researches and studies and revised the draft of the article.

Declaration of conflicting interests

The author declares that he is not in conflict of financial or non-financial interests for the data and information presented in the manuscript.

Fig. 2 Extranodal lesions of aggressive NHL

Fig. 3 The presence of signs of intoxication in primarily diagnosed patients

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